

Synthesis, spectral and antimicrobial studies of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal chelate polymers of poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid

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Abstract : Metal chelate polymers of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid have been synthesized and characterized by IR and electronic spectral studies. The synthesized poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid and its chelate polymers were screened for their antimicrobial activities against bacteria, viz. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungi, viz. *Aspergillus awamori*. Poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid was found to exhibit moderate biological activity against both bacteria and fungi which increased in the forms of their metal chelate polymers.

Keywords : Synthesis, antimicrobial studies, metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid, poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid, metal chelate polymers.

Introduction

Polymers are important materials used in commodities such as textiles, tires and packaging (e.g. film and containers). Polymers, particularly thermosets, are widely used as composite materials in applications in the transportation industry, including automotive, marine and aerospace. A large number of chelate/coordination polymers have wide applications in waste water treatment¹, pollution control², hydrometallurgy³, preconcentration⁴, anionic polyelectrolyte hydrogels⁵ and as cation-exchange resins⁶.

Poly(hydroxamic acids) and their metal chelates have attracted interest in many scientific and technological fields. Copper(II) metal complexes of hydroxamic acid polymer⁷ have been reported to prevent the decay of wood, cellulose and hemicellulose significantly. The various hydroxamic acid polymer chelating resins have been found applications in some fields, such as removal of harmful trace metal, ions recovery from sea water⁸⁻¹¹, drinking water¹² and extraction of gold, silver, copper, iron, nickel, cobalt and zinc from dilute acid solutions¹³.

Some ion exchange resins, based on hydroxamic acids and a number of hydroxamic acids are currently accepted as therapeutic (desferrioxamine B, hydroxycarbamide, iboproxam, oxametacin, bufexamac,

adrafinil)¹⁴ and antimicrobial^{15,16} agents. Recently, poly(hydroxamic acid) have also been used as breathable chemical and biological detoxifying protective fabrics¹⁷. The promising importance of this class of compounds prompted us to synthesize and screen antimicrobial activity of poly(metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid) and its metal chelate polymers.

Experimental

Methyl metha acrylate was obtained from Loba Chemie, Mumbai and used after redistillation, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (Qualigenes) was used as received, azobisisobutyronitrile (CDH) was used after recrystallization. All the solvents were distilled before use, except DMF (Merck) and acetic acid (Qualigenes) which were used as received. IR spectra were recorded in KBr in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ on Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz) FT-NMR. Thermal analysis was done using Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DTA instrument under nitrogen atmosphere and at a heating rate of 10 °C/min and electronic spectra of chelate polymer were recorded on Varian Cary 5E, UV-NIS-NIR spectrophotometer

*Synthesis of metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid* · 13.9 g (0.2 mol) hydroxylamine hydrochloride was dissolved

in 80 ml methanol and 10 ml (0.1 mol) methyl methacrylate was added to it. Now, 60 ml methanolic KOH (5 mol) solution was added drop wise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 30 h and then solvent was removed under vacuum. Solid residue, thus obtained, was acidified with 50 ml acetic acid/water (50 : 50; v/v) and extracted with ethyl acetate (60 ml) for two times. Then, 30 ml toluene was added to the extract and allow to diffuse. The mixture was kept for 30 min for the evaporation of solvent. White colored granules were obtained which were washed with diethyl ether for several times and dried in vacuum oven at 50 °C. The metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid was melts at 182 °C.

Synthesis of poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid : 120 mg recrystallized azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) was taken in clean and dry 250 ml three necked round bottom flask. To this, 50 ml solution of metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid [1.2 g metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid dissolved in 50 ml water and DMF solution (95 : 5, v/v)] was added. The mixture was heated at 60 °C under nitrogen atmosphere then allowed to cool at room temperature and poured on crushed ice-methanol mixture. White precipitate, thus obtained, was washed with alcohol followed by diethyl ether. Finally, it was dried under vacuum at 60 °C, white granular powder was obtained. The poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid becomes blackish at 212 °C and decomposed at 245 °C.

Synthesis of chelate polymers : 0.20 g (0.002 mol) poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid was dissolved in 25 ml water and mixed with 15–20 ml aqueous solutions (0.001 mol) of 0.245 g manganese acetate tetrahydrate/0.249 g cobalt acetate tetrahydrate/0.248 g nickel acetate tetrahydrate/0.199 g copper acetate monohydrate. The mixtures were well stirred for 15–20 min at pH 5 and refluxed on water bath for about 5 to 6 h. The hot solutions were allowed to cool at room temperature and kept in refrigerator for over night. The colored crystalline solids were obtained which were filtered, washed with alcohol followed by ether and then dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in vacuum desiccators.

Results and discussion

The IR spectra of metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid and poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid show an absorption peak in the region 3500–3400 cm⁻¹ due to -OH stretching vibrations. This band is disappeared in the IR spectra of metal chelates polymers which suggests the coordination of ligand with metal ion through

deprotonation¹⁸ of -OH group. In the IR spectra of chelate polymers appearance of broad bands around 3475–3430 cm⁻¹ and 875–820 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of water molecules in the coordinating sphere. A broad band in the region 3250–3140 cm⁻¹ is probable due to N-H stretching vibrations. A sharp band in the region 2985–2930 cm⁻¹ is probably due to aliphatic C-H stretching vibrations¹⁹. In the IR spectra of metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid and poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid, the carbonyl stretching frequency observed in the region 1660–1620 cm⁻¹. This band has shifted towards lower frequency region by 40–30 cm⁻¹, in the case of chelate polymers²⁰, which indicates the coordination of ligand to metal through >C=O group. A medium sharp intensity band in the region 1096–1020 cm⁻¹ is observed in the infra-red spectra of ligand which may be attributed due to stretching vibrations of -N=O group in coordination with metal ion. All chelate polymers exhibit new band around 575–550 cm⁻¹ which may be due to the formation of M-O bonds²¹.

Metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid and poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid show singlet at δ 11.13 and 10.897 ppm respectively which may be attributed due to proton of N-OH group, another singlet in the range of δ 7.85–7.72 ppm due to -CO-NH group. Both hydroxamic acids exhibit double doublet in the range δ 7.50–7.55 ppm and δ 6.61–6.65 ppm and δ 7.32–7.34 ppm and δ 6.32–6.34 ppm due to -CH₂ group. A singlet in the range of δ 2.33–2.30 ppm is also appeared in the spectra of both the hydroxamic acids which may be attributed due to -CH₃ protons. Poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid shows singlet at δ 1.39 ppm which may be attributed due to isobutyro group.

In the thermogram, three steps decomposition are observed. The first step decomposition is started at 225 °C, the corresponding weight loss is 40.23% and the maximum rate of decomposition for the poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid was 450.70°C. The second step of decomposition is started at 470 °C, the corresponding weight loss is 24.98% with peak temperature 512.15 °C. The third step decomposition is started at 605 °C the corresponding weight loss is 22.75% with minimum rate of decomposition for the poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid was 772.50 °C. The poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid is almost completely degraded at above 840 °C, remaining only 8.208% char residue.

The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} chelate polymer show three bands in the region 16000–21500, 22000–25500

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid, poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid and its metal chelate polymers

Sl. no.	Compd.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>		<i>Aspergillus awamori</i>	
		Concentrations (mg/ml)	Growth inhibition zone (mm)	Concentrations (mg/ml)	Growth inhibition zone (mm)
1.	Metha acryloyl- <i>N</i> -hydroxamic acid	2.525	10	2.525	0.0
		1.263	9		
		0.631	8		
2.	Poly(metha acryloyl)- <i>N</i> -hydroxamic acid	2.525	12	2.525	65
		1.263	10		
		0.631	9		
3.	Mn ^{II} metal chelate polymer of poly(metha acryloyl)- <i>N</i> -hydroxamic acid	2.525	14	2.525	45
		1.263	12		
		0.631	10		
4.	Co ^{II} metal chelate polymer of poly(metha acryloyl)- <i>N</i> -hydroxamic acid	2.525	18	2.525	40
		1.263	16		
		0.631	12		
5.	Ni ^{II} metal chelate polymer of poly(metha acryloyl)- <i>N</i> -hydroxamic acid	2.525	16	2.525	20
		1.263	14		
		0.631	12		
6.	Cu ^{II} metal chelate polymer of poly(metha acryloyl)- <i>N</i> -hydroxamic acid	2.525	20	2.525	15
		1.263	16		
		0.631	10		

and 26000–28000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions $^4A_{1g} \rightarrow ^6A_{1g}$, $^4E_g(D) \rightarrow ^6A_{1g}$ and $^4E_g(D) \rightarrow ^6A_{1g}$ respectively which suggest the octahedral geometry²² for this chelate polymer.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} chelate polymer show three bands in the region 11000–15000, 15500–18000 and 19500–22000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$, $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. Hence, it is suggested that the Co^{II} chelate polymer has octahedral geometry²³.

The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} chelate polymer exhibit three bands in the region 12000–15000, 15500–19500 and 24000–27500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$, $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$ and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively which suggests an octahedral geometry²³.

The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} chelate polymer displays three bands in the region 11500–15500, 16000–18500 and 22500–25500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g} \rightarrow ^2E_{1g}$ and $^2A_{2g}$ respectively which are in good agreement with the distorted octahedral geometry²⁴.

On the basis of IR, ¹H NMR and electronic spectral data its seems reasonable to assume the M^{II} chelate polymers have the following structure (Fig. 1).

where $M^{2+} = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} and $n = 2, 3$.

Fig. 1. Probable structure of metal chelate polymers.

Antimicrobial studies :

The synthesized metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid, poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid and its metal chelate polymers were tested for their biological activities against bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungi *Aspergillus awamori* by adopting serial dilution method²⁵.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were determined at the end of incubation period of 24 h at 37 °C for bacteria and 84 h at 28 °C for fungi. The results have been presented in Table 1. The results show that the antimicrobial activity of metha acryloyl-*N*-hydroxamic acid has increased in the form of poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid which further increased in the form metal chelate polymers of poly(metha acryloyl)-*N*-hydroxamic acid. Among the metal chelate polymers, Cu^{II} metal chelate polymers was found most active against both bacteria and fungi. The increased²⁶ antimicrobial activity of metal chelate polymers may be due to the fact that chelation or coordination reduces the polarity of the metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possibly *p*-electron delocalization within the whole chelate ring. This process thus increases the lipophilic nature of the compound, which, in turn, favors penetration through the bacterial wall of the microorganism. The Cu^{II}-chelate polymers widest effective antimicrobial due to higher stability constant²⁷.

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